

“XXI ASR O'ZBEK ADABIYOTI MANZARALARI”

THE VALUE OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Ruxshona Murodillayeva

Zokirxon qizi

The student of Andijan State Pedagogical

murodillayevruxshona@gmail.com

Annotation: There are several nations, countries and at the same time languages in the world. Language is the source of nation's spirituality and culture. As long as the nation has its own language, it means that it has something to say to the world. And language is primarily a means of communication.¹

Dunyoda bir qancha xalqlar, mamlakatlar va ayni paytda tillar mavjud. Til xalq ma'naviyati va madaniyatining manbaidir. Millatning o'z tili bor ekan, demak, uning dunyoga aytadigan gapi bor. Til esa birinchi navbatda muloqot vositasidir.¹

В мире существует множество наций, стран и одновременно языков. Язык – источник духовности и культуры нации. Пока у нации есть свой язык, это значит, что ей есть что сказать миру. А язык - это, прежде всего, средство общения.¹

Key words: language, independence, educational, culture, world, Uzbek, freedom, alphabet.

Introduction:

In recent years, our country has undergone such changes and updates that the speed, scope and universality of these changes are mind-boggling. In a short period of time, the buildings and structures that are being erected, the factories that are being put into operation, the educational and health centers that are being put into use, recreation centers, sports, art and culture centers are all being built for the people, for you and for us. In the period after our independence, for the first time,

“XXI ASR O'ZBEK ADABIYOTI MANZARALARI”

the idea of bringing human interests to the center of our state's activities, which represents the essence of independence, was put forward. It has been a long-standing dream mankind to live and make a living in a place where all conditions are created for every person to live a free, independent life, to fully express his capabilities and abilities.² In order for this dream of a person to come true, for the country where he lives to provide a truly free and happy life, certain economic, social, political and legal conditions must exist in this country. In this place, attention to human rights and freedoms should be at the highest level. Because in order for a person to feel independent and happy, first of all, his rights and freedoms must be ensured.³

HISTORY OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE:

The old Uzbek language, in which the masterpieces of our classical poets such as Lutfi, Atoyi, Alisher Navoiy, Babur, Mashrab, Ogahiy, Feruz, Muqimiy and Furkat were written from the 12th and 13th centuries to the beginning of the 20th century, was the basis for the formation and development of the modern Uzbek language. The literary language of the Karakhanid period also served as the basis for the formation of the Uzbek language. The two literary language traditions of this period—the eastern (Qarluq-Uyghur) literary language and the western (Kipchog-Oguz) literary language – served to form the Uzbek language. In particular, the epic poem “Qissayi Yusuf” (1239) by Qul Ali, written in the western linguistic tradition, and the work “Qisasyi Rabguzi” (1309-1310) by Rabguzi, written in the eastern linguistic tradition, represent the period when the Uzbek literary language was formed. The term Uzbek is first mentioned in history in the 12th century in Rashiddin's “History of the Mongols” in the sense of a nobleman. One of the commanders of Jaloliddin Manguberdi was called Uzbektoy. The word Uzbek itself has meanings such as “bek”, “horseman”, “simple”, “honest”, “generous”, “people-loving”, “heart-warming”, “beloved”. Herman Vamberi's “Turkish Folk Art” defines the word “Uzbek” as follows: “When asking

what the word “Uzbek” means, first of all, it should be noted that this word consists of the words “o’z” and “bek”, the first of which means “true”, “wonderful”, “the bottom is solid”, “leader”. The stability of the term Uzbek in our language compared to previously used terms such as Turk, Sart and Chigatay is due to the settlement and seizure of power by Uzbek tribes led by Shaybani Khan in Central Asia. While dozens and hundreds of linguists such as Atoyi, Sakkokiy and Lutfiy contributed to the improvement of Uzbek language, Mevlana Alisher Navoi made its reputation known to the world. During the Navoi era and the period before Navoi, the Uzbek language was known as the Turkic language, with the name of the Turkic language. From the 16th century, the names of Uzbek clans became the names of the entire people.⁴

The number of words used by the world’s prominent writers:

Alisher Navoi 26 035;

Alexander Pushkin 21 193;

William Shakespeare over 20 000;

Miguel de Cervantes over 18 000;

Abdurahmon Jomi 17 600;

Abdulla Tokay over 14 000.⁵

Arabic alphabet: Since the 10th century, Uzbek script has been carried out in the Arabic alphabet in the territory of Uzbekistan.

Latin alphabet (1928): Soviet power the transition to the Latin alphabet began in 1928.

Cyrillic alphabet (1940): Since 1940, the Uzbek language has been written in the Cyrillic alphabet.

Return to the Latin alphabet (1993): After independence, in 1993, a writing system based on the Latin alphabet was again formalized.⁶

INTERJECTIONS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE:

When determining the number of Uzbek speakers, one thing should be taken into account: the number of Uzbek speakers is not equal to the number of people of Uzbek ethnicity. Therefore, the data reflected in national statistics do not fully determine linguistic affiliation. The issue of language is studied separately in surveys.

According to the 2019 data:

Uzbekistan 22-25 million;

Afghanistan 2.9-3.2 million;

Tajikistan 1.3-2 million;

Kyrgyzstan 1.2 million;

Turkmenistan 600 thousand;

Other countries 100-200 thousand.⁷

But the number of people who know Uzbek as a second or third language is relatively higher. Let's say that the absolute majority of citizens of Uzbekistan know Uzbek, at least 30 million. There are also tens of thousands of people in neighboring republics who have learned Uzbek as a result of living with Uzbeks. They are also joined by people who are learning Uzbek.

Based on the data from 2022:

“Currently, the number of Uzbek speakers on earth has exceeded 60 million, and the Uzbek language is taught in more than 50 higher education institutions in foreign countries” the report says. (from the event held in the city of Mecca)⁸

It was reported that the event participants were provided with a detailed briefing on the ongoing efforts in Uzbekistan to reinforce the status of the Uzbek language and to elevate the international prestige of the mother tongue. In this context, it was

highlighted that numerous Uzbek language centers have been established at various universities abroad, and the number of individuals interested in studying Uzbek in foreign countries is steadily increasing year by year. At the meeting, representatives of the Bukhara Uzbek diaspora residing in Saudi Arabia noted that preserving the Uzbek language, which reflects their ethnic identity, enhancing its status within the community, and raising the younger generation with respect for their mother tongue are becoming increasingly urgent tasks.

REFERENCES:

1. Islom Karimov. Yuksak Ma'naviyat Yengilmas Kuch ISBN 978-9943-04-075-5 (2008)
2. Yusufalievich, M. S., & Maripjon o'g'li, X. O. (2022). Natural Emergency Situations and Protection of the Population from their Effects. Central Asian Journal Of Theoretical and Applied Science, 3(5), 379-383.
3. Rahnomoyevich, D. M., & Yusufalievich, M. S. (2021). Life Safety As A Secure Way Of Interaction With The Environment. The American Journal of Applied sciences, 3(04), 208-213.
4. N.Erkaboyeva. (2016) ISBN: 978-9943-995-19-2 “The collection of lectures in the Uzbek language”
5. Comparative linguistic statistics on literary vocabulary-compiled from various linguistic studies cited in Erkaboyeva (2016)
6. Historical timeline adapted from Erkaboyeva and related Uzbek linguistic sources.
7. National statistics data (2019) summarized from Uzbekistan language demographics.